

FIVE YEARS OF INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ON A SMALL KARST ISLAND OF VIS (CROATIA)

PET GODINA INTERDISCIPLINARNIH ISTRAŽIVANJA MALOG KRŠKOG OTOKA VISA (HRVATSKA)

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APSTRAKT: Otok Vis, mali pučinski krški otok u Jadranskom moru, ima jedinstvene geološke i hidrogeološke značajke, što mu omogućuje autonomnost vodoopskrbe. Glavno vodocrpilište, zdenačko polje Korita, nalazi se u centralnom dijelu otoka gdje je hidrogeološkim barijerama zaštićeno od prodora mora. Trenutačni kapacitet crpljenja (maksimalno 42 l/s) zadovoljava većinu potražnje, no intenzivan ljetni turizam i klimatske promjene vrše značajan pritisak na resurse podzemne vode tijekom sušne sezone. Posljedično, tijekom proteklog desetljeća došlo je do povremenih redukcija za potrošače. Tijekom proteklih pet godina, izvršena su interdisciplinarna istraživanja s ciljem (i) sprečavanja degradacije kvalitativnog i količinskog stanja podzemne vode, (ii) osiguravanja održivog korištenja podzemnih voda, (iii) određivanja novih perspektivnih lokacija za buduće vodozahvate, te (iv) pronalaska alternativnih rješenja za postizanje održive vodoopskrbe (npr. umjetno prihranjivanje vodonosnika). Glavni zaključci istraživanja, utemeljeni na detaljnim geološkim, hidrogeološkim, hidrološkim, geofizičkim, klimatološkim i ekonomskim podacima ukazuju da se održivo upravljanje i korištenje podzemne vode na otoku Visu može postići povećanjem crpnih količina uz uspostavu sustava ranog upozoravanja na prodor morske vode, uspostavom umjetnog prihranjivanja vodonosnika, smanjenjem gubitaka iz vodoopskrbnog sustava te planskim i održivim turizmom.

Glavne riječi: hidrogeologija, krški vodonosnik, prodor mora, otok Vis

ABSTRACT: Vis, a small and remote karst island in the Adriatic Sea, exhibits peculiar geological and hydrogeological settings, resulting in the island's autonomous water supply. The main water supply site, the Korita well field, is in the central part of the island, where it is protected from seawater intrusions by hydrogeological barriers. The current pumping capacity (maximum of 42 l/s) meets most of the demand, however, intensive summer tourism and climate change exert high stress on groundwater resources during the dry season. Consequently, in the last decade, occasional reductions for consumers occurred. During the past five years, interdisciplinary research was carried out with the aim of (i) mitigating the degradation of the qualitative and quantitative state of groundwater, (ii) ensuring the sustainable use of groundwater, (iii) determining new prospective locations for future wells, and (iv) finding alternative solutions to achieve sustainable water supply (e.g., managed aquifer recharge). The main conclusions of the research, based on detailed geological, hydrogeological, hydrological, geophysical, climatological and economic data, indicate that the sustainable management and exploitation of groundwater on the island of Vis can be achieved by increasing pumping rates with the establishment of an early warning system for seawater intrusion, by the deployment of managed aquifer recharge, reduction of losses from the water supply system, as well as fostering of sustainable tourism.

Key words: hydrogeology, karst aquifer, seawater intrusion, Vis island

INTRODUCTION

Karst rocks are among the most important aquifers in the world, providing groundwater resources for almost a quarter of the global population (Ford & Williams 2007). Karst aquifers are significantly different compared to aquifers with intergranular porosity, since the process of carbonate rock dissolution (i.e., karstification) results in heterogeneous and anisotropic hydrogeological properties (Goldscheider & Andreo 2007), posing a significant challenge for their investigation, utilization, and management. In the Mediterranean region, where karst groundwater resources are highly vulnerable, limited, and unevenly distributed, sustainable groundwater management remains one of the key environmental challenges (García-Ruiz et al. 2011). Climate change, overexploitation, improper land use, user conflicts, and seawater intrusions are the most common drivers of degradation of groundwater quality and availability. In particular, the Mediterranean region is often regarded as a hot spot of climate change with a predicted air temperature increase of 3.5–5.5 °C until 2100 (Branković et al. 2013) and an increase in precipitation variability with a negative influence on water balance (Aguilera & Murillo 2008). Furthermore,

environmental challenges are aggravated by rising anthropic pressure and high population density, with the local population drastically increasing during the dry summer tourist season.

In Croatia, merely a few islands have a completely autonomous water supply from karst aquifers, fresh water lens, and freshwater lakes (e.g., Vis, Cres), whereas the majority are connected to the water supply systems on the mainland (Borović et al. 2019). The most significant problem regarding groundwater utilisation on Croatian islands is seawater intrusion. This problem is caused by (i) small surface area and low relief of the islands, resulting in small catchments and low hydraulic gradients, (ii) intense fracturing and karstification with a karst base level below the present sea-level resulting in high permeability of the rock mass and preferential seawater intrusion through karstic conduits, and (iii) climate of the area characterised by relatively low precipitation and high evapotranspiration (Terzić et al. 2010).

The study area is the island of Vis, a small island (89.7 km²) in the central part of the Adriatic Sea, approximately 50 km from the Croatian mainland. Vis belong to the geotectonic unit of the External Dinarides, an area characterized by deep and irregular karstification. It exhibits a composite and peculiar structural fabric (Korbar et al. 2012) affecting its hydrogeological setting. The main lithological units are: (i) Cretaceous limestone and dolomites, (ii) the volcanic-sedimentary-evaporite (VSE) complex of the Komiža bay (Middle to Upper Triassic) in the western part of the island, consisting of gypsum, dolomite-gypsum breccias, karst debris, andesites, volcanic agglomerates, siltites, marls, and tuffites, and (iii) Quaternary deposits, represented by the *terra rossa* cover in karst poljes, and locally, aeolian sands and colluvial deposits (Figure 1) (Terzić et al. 2022).

Figure 1. a) Hydrogeological map of the island of Vis with sampling locations and b) schematic hydrogeological cross-section (modified after Terzić et al. 2022)

The climate of the island can be classified as a Mediterranean climate with dry and hot summers. In the period from 1991 to 2019, the mean annual air temperature was 17.1 °C and the mean annual precipitation was 775 mm. Mean annual evapotranspiration is approximately 65%. Due to its remote position in the open sea, the island is not connected to the public water supply system on the mainland and relies exclusively on its own water resources. Groundwater is recharged exclusively by precipitation. Currently, the system satisfies the freshwater demand of the local population (approximately 3300). However, a fivefold increase in demand during the tourist season exerts high stress on freshwater resources and several reductions for consumers occurred in the last decades. The water supply system of Vis consists of five wells (BO1 to BO5) drilled in the Korita well field in the central part of the island, two wells (K1 and B1) in the Komiža hinterland, and the coastal spring Pizdica. The maximum pumping capacity at Korita well field is 42 l/s, and the groundwater quality is excellent since hydrogeological barriers protect it from seawater intrusions. Wells K1 and B1, and the Pizdica spring in the western part of the island provide approximately 5 l/s in total.

Detailed knowledge on functioning of karst system is a prerequisite for its sustainable management and long-term planning. In this paper, we present the initial results of hydrogeological, geochemical, and geophysical investigations to detail the hydrogeological setting of the karstic aquifer and the physical and chemical characteristics of the groundwater.

METHODOLOGY

Field investigation included in situ monitoring of pH, temperature, O₂ saturation, and electrical conductivity (EC) by WTW multi-parameter probe. Furthermore, alkalinity, i.e., the concentration of bicarbonate ions, was determined by volumetric titration. Laboratory investigations were performed in the hydrochemical laboratory of the Department of Hydrogeology and Engineering Geology at the Croatian Geological Survey. Principal ion composition (HCO₃, Cl, SO₄, NO₃, Ca, Mg, Na, K) was analyzed by ion chromatography on DIONEX ICS-6000 DP (Thermo Fischer Scientific Inc., Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). Laboratory for low-level radioactivities of Ruđer Bošković Institute conducted the determination of tritium activity concentration by the method of electrolytic enrichment using the liquid scintillation counter Quantulus 1220.

Electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) survey was conducted in June 2020 to assess the soil–rock interface and the rock mass quality and to delineate the depth of the groundwater table. A 2D-ERT was carried out using the POLARES 2.0 electrical imaging system (P.A.S.I. srl), which uses a sinusoidal alternate current of adjustable frequency. The RES2DINV resistivity inversion software was used to automatically invert the apparent resistivity data from the field into two-dimensional resistivity subsurface models.

Since fluid flow in carbonate aquifers is generally dominated by fractures and karstic conduits, it is fundamental to study the geometrical attributes of fractures. High-resolution structural measurements, including orientation, kinematics, and crosscutting relationships, were performed. Orientations of deformation structures were plotted using the Daisy 3 software in stereographic projections (Wulff lower hemisphere stereonet).

RESULTS

Hydrochemical facies of the groundwater enable the determination of the relationship between the chemical properties of water, rock lithology, and local groundwater flow. Major ion concentration were plotted on trilinear Piper diagram (Figure 2), and three main hydrochemical facies could be distinguished:

- Ca-HCO₃ type: BO2, BO5, DP1, DRV, and K1
- Mixed type: GUS, KAM, and AB
- Na-Cl type: PIZ and V1

All groundwater samples show relative abundance in Ca, Mg, and HCO₃, which is expected given the predominant carbonate lithology of the aquifers on the island of Vis. The first group (squares in Fig. 2), corresponding to primarily Ca-HCO₃ hydrochemical facies, is characterized by Ca>>Mg>Na>K and HCO₃>>Cl>SO₄>NO₃, relatively low EC (mean values <1000 μS/cm), and low to moderate Cl concentrations. The second group (triangles in Fig. 2), representing mixed facies, consists of two SO₄ rich groundwater samples from GUS and KAM, where Ca>>Mg~Na>K and HCO₃>SO₄> Cl>NO₃, as well as sample from coastal well AB where Na and Cl prevail. The third group (circles in Fig. 2) is represented by a spring and a well with relatively higher Cl concentrations and higher EC values, corresponding primarily to Na-Cl hydrochemical facies. The separation between the three distinctive water groups is relatively well-defined, while the intermediate chemical composition of some groundwater samples reflects the higher effect of

specific hydrogeological processes on groundwater chemistry (e.g., stronger mixing with seawater, stronger dissolution of gypsum).

Figure 2. Piper diagram of groundwater samples from the island of Vis (from January 2020 to December 2023)

Given the composite lithological structure of the island of Vis, the molar ratios $Ca/(Ca+Mg)$ and $SO_4/(SO_4+HCO_3)$ were utilized to assess the dominant dissolution process in groundwater samples on the island of Vis (Figure 3).

$Ca/(Ca+Mg)$ ratio commonly ranges from 0.5 to 1, representing the dissolution of stoichiometric dolomite and calcite (i.e., pure limestone), respectively. Additionally, an increase in SO_4 concentration is indicative of dissolution of evaporite minerals. The diagram in Fig. 3 shows predominantly dolomite dissolution in samples from the Na-Cl group, while samples from Ca- HCO_3 group are characterized by intermediate values, implying mixed dissolution of limestone and dolomite. Samples from the mixed group are also characterized by mixed dissolution of limestone and dolomite, whereas springs KAM and GUS show a significant increase in SO_4 concentrations and plot towards gypsum end member. Both springs occur with the zone of the VSE complex of the Komiža bay, where scattered gypsum outcrops are commonly found on surface, while anhydrite or other less- common evaporite minerals have not been recorded. Gypsum outcrops are also present in the discharge zone of the spring PIZ, whose groundwater is characterized by intermediate values of SO_4 . Conversely, well V1, which is located in the hinterland and catchment of spring PIZ, shows the lowest values of SO_4 , confirming the relatively narrow and scattered extent of the VSE zone in the western part of the island. Minor effect of gypsum dissolution is reflected in SO_4 concentration in spring DRV, which is also located in the zone of the VSE complex. Furthermore, a relative increase in Mg accompanied by an increase in SO_4 suggests that groundwater from springs GUS and KAM is affected by dedolomitization, a common process in aquifers which contain both dolomite and gypsum. The mechanism of dedolomitization is driven by the dissolution of gypsum, causing excess Ca and calcite precipitation, and the consequent dissolution of dolomite followed by an increase of Mg in the groundwater.

Figure 3. Diagram of $\text{Ca}/(\text{Ca}+\text{Mg})$ and $\text{SO}_4/(\text{SO}_4+\text{HCO}_3)$ molar ratios

Furthermore, the molar ratio of Na and Cl was explored to investigate the occurrence, source, and extent of groundwater salinization on the island of Vis (Figure 4).

The ratio of 1:1 implies the dissolution of pure halite, higher ratio indicates excess Na as a result of weathering of silicate minerals or cation exchange processes, whereas Na and Cl ratios lower than those of seawater (i.e., 0.86) indicate seawater intrusion, reverse ion exchange or anthropogenic contamination (Appelo & Postma 2005). Given that no halite mineralization was ever recorded on the island of Vis, the primary saline sources are seawater intrusion, infiltration of chloride-rich marine aerosols, and atmospheric deposition. Two distinctive clusters are evident in Fig. 4, Ca-HCO₃ group and mixed group (springs KAM and GUS) with low concentrations of Na and Cl, and Na-Cl group and coastal well AB with significantly higher concentrations of Na and Cl. This is concordant with the structural fabric of the island, where high permeability carbonates, situated along the coast, act as preferential flowpaths for seawater intrusion, hence the higher concentrations in the Na-Cl group. Conversely, geological structures and hydrogeological barriers impede significant intrusion in more distant wells and springs of the low salinity Ca-HCO₃ group. The fact that even the most salinized groundwater from the island of Vis displays chloride concentrations on the threshold of fresh water and brackish water indicates that seawater intrusion is not too extensive even during prolonged dry periods, implying favorable and balance hydrostatic regime with relatively small but sufficient fresh groundwater reserves within the island's aquifers. The seawater percentage is very low (<1%) in the majority of the samples, except in the Na-Cl group and well AB (>1%).

Analyses of ³H activity were performed on samples from BO2, Pizdica, and K1 during the hydrological minimum in September 2020. The results (in TU – Tritium units) were 1.68 ± 0.72 , 2.3 ± 1.0 , and 2.3 ± 1.1 for BO2, K1, and Pizdica, respectively. These waters can be classified as a mixture of sub-modern and modern water (0.8-4 TU; Motzer 2007). The lower TU in BO2 possibly indicates a shift towards older groundwater, reflecting the exploitation of a deeper resource.

Figure 4. Biplot diagram of Na and Cl molar ratios

Electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) survey was conducted in the karst polje Dol, in the vicinity the Korita well field, as subsurface and groundwater data are scarce in this area (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. ERT profile in Dol polje

The results showed a low resistivity zone (15-110 Ωm) interpreted as topsoil (i.e., terra rossa) above a high resistivity bedrock. Resistivity increases with depth, and the high resistivity bedrock was divided in several zones: i) upper weathering zone (110-250 Ωm), where open discontinuities with weathered walls are infilled with clay and rock fragments; ii) lower weathering zone (250-700 Ωm), where discontinuities have small apertures and moderate to negligible infilling; iii) compact carbonates (>700 Ωm). In the middle section of the profile, at a depth of 0-20 m a.s.l., an anomaly with a resistivity of 300-500 Ωm was observed, indicating a potential groundwater target.

Structural-geological investigations were performed in 15 sites along the Komiža-Vis road and around the Korita well field, where the Komiža-Vis fault system is observed in tectonized Cretaceous carbonates (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Simplified geological map of the island of Vis after Korbar et al. (2012). Structural measurement sites are in orange and numbered 1-15. Deformation structures are plotted in stereographic projections lower hemisphere Wulff nets.

The collected dataset was dominated by high-angle (mostly $>60^\circ$) deformation structures, namely faults, fractures, veins, and stylolites. In sites 3 to 15 along the Komiža-Vis fault (Fig. 6), the deformation pattern is constituted by a set of sinistral strike-slip fault planes striking roughly $N70^\circ$, i.e. subparallel to the fault system, and associated with NE-SW veins and roughly NW-SE striking pressure solution planes, coherent with sinistral shear sense. A subsidiary set of sinistral, $N40^\circ$ striking fault planes, splaying from the E-W striking fault planes, was in turn associated with N-S veins. Moving away from the Komiža-Vis fault zone towards the S (sites 8 and 14), fault planes and associated veins were organized in two orthogonal

sets: N100°-110° and N10°-20°. Fault cores of pluridecametric fault segments are composed of chaotic breccias infiltrated by terra rossa, while minor faults splay in their damage zones showing crackle breccia pockets and abundant striae and clear to reddish calcite slickenlines. The same type of calcite occurs in the described vein sets. Fractures, which include both joints and other deformation elements overprinted by abundant meteoric dissolution, were found in all the aforementioned orientations. Sites 1 and 2 are hosted in the dolostones close to the Komiža diapir contact and showed slightly different deformation structures. Site 1 shows a principal sinistral strike-slip fault plane, striking N80°, and associated veins. This fault plane was abutted by mutually crosscutting dextral NE-SW, sinistral NW-SE fault planes, and N-S cleavage planes. Fault cores of principal faults in dolostones were characterized by intense cataclasis and dolomite cementation, which occurs also in the associated veins and constitutes slickenlines of the subsidiary fault planes. Site 2 showed bedding dipping 45° to the ENE and slickenlines indicating extensional, sinistral, and dextral kinematics. Here, four fault sets were observed: (i) N-S bedding-orthogonal extensional faults, (ii) high angle, N70° striking, mostly sinistral faults, (iii) subvertical NW-SE trending, sinistral faults, and (iv) NE-SW faults and fractures, filled by terra rossa. In this latter area, complex transtensional kinematics are the result of the interaction of the diapir contact and the Komiža-Vis fault.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study describes a segment of multidisciplinary approach for the assessment of karst groundwater resources on the island of Vis. The main conclusions after the first phase of the research, i.e., after five continuous years of investigations are:

1. Groundwater exploited at the Korita well field displays long-term stability (i.e., ion composition, electrical conductivity), despite lower-than-average precipitation in the last five years. This suggests relatively large groundwater reserves with a good resilience towards seasonal over-pumping and droughts.
2. Groundwater quality at the Korita well field is excellent, since the aquifer is protected by hydrogeological barriers from the west (volcanic-sedimentary-evaporite complex of the Komiža bay) and from the south (infilled rock-mass of reduced permeability below karst poljes).
3. Most dangerous pathways for seawater intrusion are from eastern and northern sides along major faults. Early warning system for seawater intrusion should be established along these directions.
4. Groundwater chemistry is affected by carbonate & gypsum dissolution, mixing with seawater, and ion exchange processes.
5. Downscaled climate change simulations for the island of Vis indicate a sharp increase in air temperature until the end of the century, resulting in higher evapotranspiration and potential reduction in infiltration, groundwater recharge, and groundwater availability.
6. Sustainable management of karst groundwater resources on the island of Vis combines the establishment of early warning system for seawater intrusion, alternative water supply solutions (e.g., managed aquifer recharge, small desalination unit, rainwater harvesting for agricultural irrigation), water reuse, and further investigations of potential areas for new wells.

Further investigations on the island of Vis will include the continuation of periodical and continuous hydrogeological/hydrochemical monitoring, thermal imaging to detect major outflow zones in the sea, 3D geological reconstruction and 3D numerical modeling of groundwater flow, hydrogeological mapping, and analyses of precipitation chemistry and patterns.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Presented research was done in the scope of the internal research project SIS-VIS at the Croatian Geological Survey, funded by the National Recovery and Resilience Plan 2021–2026 of the European Union – NextGenerationEU, and monitored by the Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Croatia, and DEEPWATER-CE project through Interreg-CE program funded by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF).

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